

WHEN *CHONGYI* BECAME A PROBLEM: REVISITING INTELLECTUAL DEBATES ON INDIRECT TRANSLATION IN 1920S-1930S CHINA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19330648>

Keywords: *Indirect translation, translation history, Lu Xun*

Indirect translation was a highly prevalent phenomenon in twentieth-century Chinese translation history. At different stages, a large number of works from diverse world cultures were translated into Chinese via pivot languages such as English, Japanese, and Russian, thereby broadening Chinese readers' knowledge and understanding of the world. Despite its significance, however, scholarly research on indirect translation remains limited. Current studies largely confine themselves to outlining the overall historical development of indirect translation in China, without in-depth discussion of key translators, theorists, and events.

This article focuses on a critical moment in the history of indirect translation in twentieth-century China—the 1920s and 1930s—and pays particular attention to the debates on indirect translation (or *chongyi*, 重譯) among influential translators and theorists such as Lu Xun, Zheng Zhenduo, Mu Mutian, Liang Shiqiu, and Mao Dun. I examine these debates as an important intellectual event in which indirect translation was consciously problematized, theorized, and normativized by Chinese intellectuals. By revisiting the historical context and reconstructing the event, this article addresses the following questions: How did indirect translation become a problem for translators and theorists? What translation concepts and socio-historical changes did the articulation of this problem reflect and respond to? What kinds of norms were formed, and through which journals, publishing houses, or series were these norms disseminated and consolidated? What impact did these theories and norms have on later practices of indirect translation? By foregrounding this significant event, this article seeks to fill a gap in the study of Chinese translation history and to lay the groundwork for a renewed and comprehensive exploration of indirect translation practices and theories in twentieth-century China.